

PROSPECTS FOR THE INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF SERVICE ENTERPRISES IN THE BUKHARA REGION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6562362>

Axmedova Feruza Khakimovna
Bukhara State University,
Lecturer at the Department of Economics,.
Master, Djumaev Bakhodir Rakhmatullaevich

Annotation: *The article provides analytical information about the ongoing reforms in the economy of our country and region, the application of innovations in the economy, the transition of our economy to the path of innovative development.*

Key words: *integration, innovative development, intellectual product, innovative process, GDP.*

With the implementation of market reforms, the integration of the country into the world community, the growing role of the world economic system in the growth of knowledge and information, the strengthening of ties between new technologies and the capital market, the transition of our economy to an innovative one, development is important..

Knowledge of the general laws and development trends in the leading developed and developing countries of the world, as well as taking into account the specific conditions of Uzbekistan, rich in natural resources, industrial and scientific and technical potential, will lead to the path of innovative development of Uzbekistan.

In the modern world, in connection with the commercialization of intellectual property, a fundamental change in the role of science and technology, each state, as well as its subordinate structures at the level of individual enterprises, allocate resources for scientific, technical and innovative activities in market conditions. that is, to develop their own innovation policy that will allow the country, region, organization and individual to effectively achieve their socio-economic goals. The service sector is no exception.

The interaction of innovation, the development of science and technology stems from the consideration of the process of creating and mastering new technology, which is the basis of the innovation process. The innovation process includes the following stages: science-technology-production-consumption. The beginning of the innovation process is associated with scientific research of a fundamental and research nature, that is, a purely theoretical type. In other

words, the study of natural features about which there is little or no information in the current period is being studied.

The results of such research are the discovery of particular or general laws and laws of nature, as well as the discovery of new material objects and substances of nature based on theoretical calculations.

The state encourages innovation in the service. This necessitates the improvement of innovative activity in our country on the basis of international requirements, in particular, the country's accession to the world community, participation in various international organizations requires that the methodological principles of innovative development comply with the requirements of international practice.

Under the current conditions, reforms should be aimed at increasing the efficiency of the national economy. The development of the service system, an integral part of it, is one of the important areas for improving the quality of life of the population, meeting its various needs⁶.

Table-1

Growth rates of gross domestic product of the Republic of Uzbekistan⁷

Economic activities	2021Q-1	2021Q-2	2021Q-3	2021Q-4
GDP	102,6	107,2	107,4	107,4
Gross value added	102,8	107,1	107,4	107,5
Agriculture, forestry and fisheries	102,7	102,1	104,1	104,0
Mining and quarrying	102,3	108,4	114,1	110,7
Manufacturing industry	105,8	109,5	108,7	108,2
Electricity, gas, steam and air conditioning	106,6	108,3	106,9	113,0
Water supply; sewerage, collection and disposal of waste	100,1	101,8	88,2	82,3
Construction	103,9	100,3	104,7	106,8
Wholesale and retail trade; repair of motor vehicles and motorcycles	103,4	110,6	112,2	112,5
Accommodation and food	110,8	117,0	118,8	118,3

⁶ <https://stat.uz/uz/rasmiy-statistika/national-accounts-2>

⁷ <https://stat.uz/uz/rasmiy-statistika/prices-and-indexes-2>

services				
Transportation and storage	92,4	115,7	118,2	115,7
Information and communication	116,3	123,4	122,0	122,0
Financial and insurance activities	110,7	112,9	99,4	105,7
Real estate activities	101,4	104,9	105,0	104,9
Professional, scientific and technical activities	99,7	117,3	110,1	109,3
Management and provision of support services activities	107,2	125,7	119,3	116,6
Public administration and defense; compulsory social security	99,2	99,9	100,0	100,4
Education	100,6	105,5	112,3	109,6
Health care and social services	100,5	108,8	104,8	104,8
Arts, entertainment and recreation	106,0	123,8	124,9	119,1
Provision of other types of services	106,5	121,6	119,1	120,3
Financial intermediation services indirectly measured (FISIM)	116,6	116,3	113,7	113,5
Net taxes on products	100,6	108,4	107,0	106,7

The table above shows the main indicators of the socio-economic development of the country, which indicates a positive growth in all the main indicators. If we consider the state of economic growth in the regions of the country on the example of the country, then in recent years the country has achieved a number of results in terms of economic growth.

As a result of studying the composition of the country's gross regional product, it became clear that the share of industry and services in the region's gross regional product is growing, while the share of agriculture is decreasing.

This indicates that the structure of the gross regional product is changing for the better.

At the same time, industrial enterprises make a worthy contribution to the development of the country's economy. Due to the moral obsolescence of production technologies used in the country's enterprises, the change in the form of ownership of enterprises in the industry, the activity of industrial enterprises has decreased over time, but at present many new enterprises with foreign investments have been created and are effectively operating. The role of industry in the region's economy is growing.

According to preliminary estimates, in January-March 2021, the gross domestic product (hereinafter - GDP) of the Republic of Uzbekistan in current prices amounted to 128 556.8 billion soums and, compared to January-March 2020, increased in real terms by 3.0%. The GDP deflator index, in relation to the prices of January-March 2020, amounted to 111.0%⁸.

In accordance with our national values, the restoration and promotion of local, traditional and urban forms of entrepreneurial activity in the service sector in cities and villages of the region, as well as the restoration of activities for the development of national crafts, it is necessary to establish soft loans to ensure that it is also advisable to expand access to loans for industry entrepreneurs and in return to further increase the level of their property security.

⁸ file:///C:/Users/user/Downloads/January-march%202021.pdf

REFERENCES

1. <https://stat.uz/uz/rasmiy-statistika/national-accounts-2>
2. <https://stat.uz/uz/rasmiy-statistika/prices-and-indexes-2>
3. <file:///C:/Users/user/Downloads/January-march%202021.pdf>
4. Turobova H., Axmedova F., Buranova M. Foreign experiences in organizing cooperation relations in Uzbekistan //ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal. – 2021. – Т. 11. – №. 3. – С. 2397-2400.
5. Feruza A. ВАЖНОСТЬ РАЗВИТИЯ СОВРЕМЕННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ И КОММУНИКАЦИОННЫХ СИСТЕМ В ТУРИЗМЕ //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 3. – №. 3.
6. Feruza A. ШИРОКОЕ РАСПРОСТРАНЕНИЕ ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В СФЕРЕ ВНУТРЕННЕГО И МЕЖДУНАРОДНОГО ТУРИЗМА //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2020. – Т. 1. – №. 1.
7. Rajabova M. MINTAQALAR IQTISODIYOTINI INNOVATSION RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 8. – №. 8.
8. Rajabova M. FEATURES OF THE PRODUCTION OF TOURIST ROUTES //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 7. – №. 7.
9. Rajabova M. CREATION OF FREE ECONOMIC ZONES IN BUKHARA: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS //ЦЕНТР НАУЧНЫХ ПУБЛИКАЦИЙ (buxdu. uz). – 2021. – Т. 7. – №. 7.